

THE ADVANTAGES OF TPR ACTIVITIES IN SECOND LANGUAGE TEACHING

Rajapova Ruzigul Mansurbek kizi

Student of Urgench state university

Marimov Azizbek Gayrat ogli,

Student of Urgench state university

Kurbonbayeva Sojidabonu Mukhtar kizi,

Student of Urgench state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6941167>

Abstract. This article gives information about the usage of TPR for teaching English to ESL learners. It describes what kinds of advantages are available in the process of using TPR activities. And it also shows how useful they are for using second language teaching process.

Keywords: TPR, activities, kids, embarrassment, boredom.

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА TPR УПРАЖНЕНИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ВТОРОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. В этой статье содержится информация об использовании TPR для обучения английскому языку изучающих ESL. Он описывает, какие преимущества доступны в процессе использования деятельности TPR. И это также показывает, насколько они полезны для использования в процессе обучения второму языку.

Ключевые слова: TPR, занятия, дети, смущение, скука.

INTRODUCTION

After the law about teaching foreign languages to pupils at their first grade at school was accepted in our country, some of teachers began to concern about how to encourage little kids to learn a foreign language without any boredom. However, others realized that they should use TPR method in second language teaching. That's why, they tried to approach TPR activities during the lesson.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to Cicih Nuraeni (2019), TPR method encourages the students' self-confident, creativity, curiosity and motivation. "Asher and his followers claim that this method is suitable to teach language for all ages of learners. Based on their studies, they argue that the use of TPR is even more effective for adult than children. Meanwhile, in spite of the studies and suggestions, teachers make use of this method mostly for teaching language to children, not to adult" (Sojuangon Rambe, 2019).

RESULTS

Teaching English to kids requires teachers more efforts and lots of experience. "Teachers of young children should be highly qualified and they should be able to understand the child psychology including the interest of young children so that the class can be effectively managed for enhanced language learning experience" (Gautam, G. 2015).

According to M. Hashemi and M.Azizinezhad (2011), in order to keep children engaged, it is necessary to supplement the activities with lots of brightly colored visuals, toys, puppets or objects. Ahmed Javid (2021), Tugba Inciman Celik and et al., (2021) considered that in TPR method, students might feel embarrassed.

However, "having more time and being allowed to mirror others reduce anxiety and the chances of embarrassment for students who struggle to respond in front of others" (Daphne Heflin, 2020). According to A. Hounhanou (2020), the implementation of the Total Physical

Response in EFL classes in the teaching of vocabulary will stimulate learners' foreign language awareness and it will activate their involvement in the learning process.

DISCUSSION

Taking all the above mentioned statements into account, advantages of TPR activities are given in the following paragraphs.

It can make students energetic while they are playing some games based on TPR method. Because the learners motivate themselves automatically in TPR activities without their teacher's instructions as a result of competitiveness of motion.

It can improve communication skills of students. In TPR activities students can get a chance of increasing their communication skills. Because they forget their embarrassment and anxiety with help of motioning activities. So that they can easily socialize with their teams and pairs.

It can reduce the feeling of boredom. Most of children are really intolerant of sitting still during the whole lesson and getting a lot of writing and reading tasks on the given theme. In this case teachers should utilize TPR activities to inspire their students to learn English well without any hesitation.

It can prevent students from losing concentration on topic. Some pupils are likely to fall asleep during the lesson owing to sedentary learning style of foreign languages without any motions. That's why, teachers should make a few pauses after each 15 minute time of the lesson passes.

It make easier to revise second language acquired knowledge. Learning something with motions make easier to revise gained knowledge on that language. Because it can help students to embody every thing related to the language with the help of motions and imaginations which they create in the learners' minds.

CONCLUSIONS

Most learners complain about that their teachers' teaching skill is not sufficient enough to motivate them to learn English adequately. The reason for this is that some teachers don't utilize TPR method even during the whole lesson. That's why, they have this kind of problem with their students. In order to prevent students from being discouraged to learn second language effectively, teachers should use different teaching methods, particularly TPR method. Because not only it can increase learners' energy in learning foreign languages and communication skills but also it can reduce anxiety, feeling of boredom and losing concentration while studying a foreign language. Furthermore, it is the best way of revising taught themes.

REFERENCES

1. Nuraeni, Cicih. (2019). Using Total Physical Response (TPR) Method on Young Learners English Language Teaching. *Metathesis: Journal of English Language, Literature, and Teaching*. 3. 26. 10.31002/metathesis.v3i1.1223.
2. Rambe, Sojuangon. (2019). Total Physical Response. *English Education: English Journal for Teaching and Learning*. 7. 45. 10.24952/ee.v7i01.1652.
3. Gautam, Ganga. (2015). Teaching English to Young Children. *Journal of NELTA Surkhet*. 4. 10.3126/jns.v4i0.12857.

4. Hashemi, Masoud & Azizinezhad, Masoud. (2011). Teaching English To Children: A Unique, Challenging Experience For Teachers, Effective Teaching Ideas. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 30. 2083-2087. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.405.
5. Javed, Ahmad. (2011). Total physical response advantages and disadvantages. Retrieved from <https://englopedia.com>.
6. T. I. Celik, Tolga Cay & Sedat Kanadli. (2021). The effect of Total Physical Response Method on Vocabulary learning/teaching: A mixed research synthesis. *English language teaching*. Vol 14. No 12.
7. Daphne Heflin. (2020). How to Use Total Physical Response (TPR) in the Classroom. Retrieved from [https://www.teachhub.com/teaching strategies](https://www.teachhub.com/teaching-strategies).
8. Hounhanou, Arlette. (2020). Promoting TPR (Total Physical Response) Method in Teaching Vocabulary for EFL Beginners in Benin Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*. 9. 23. 10.7575/aiac.ijalel.v.9n.6p.23.